

**A Comparative Study Between Traditional and Digital Games Among Literate Adolescents
(With Reference to Raipur and Ranchi)**

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Abstract:

A decade ago, children as well as adolescents were noticed nurturing their sporty talents in the fields since the sunrise. The scenario was similar in afternoon hours when these children returned from school and started devoting time for outdoor games like kite flying, playing football or indoor games involving carom and chess. One could notice this genre playing hide and seek or running around the vicinity of their colonies. Such trend of traditional sports balancing physical and mental abilities continued unless digital media did not influence communication within society. The availability of video games, online games, game software or applications on smart phones, social media and computer has slowly affected inclination towards traditional games. Considering this topic, research problems were to find which among the two types of games is preferred more by adolescents, does any of this influence their behaviour and which medium is accessed more for playing digital games? The survey covered 30 adolescents each of Raipur and Ranchi. It was found that the dependency of these adolescents has increased on digital games and particularly on mobile phones. Moreover, they find a behavioural change by playing these games. It was also seen that more Raipur adolescents access the games for education while those of Ranchi access for mission-oriented games. However, most of the target audience also believe that traditional games improve mental and physical health. Digital games further affect their communication. In fact, they find themselves calmer and more composed.

Keywords: Traditional Games, Digital Games, Adolescent, Communication, Education

Introduction:

During the period between childhood and adulthood, as for other life stages, there are certain developmental tasks to be accomplished before one can move on to the next stage of maturity. This 'in between period' is termed adolescence. It is the phase between the onset of puberty and the

cessation of physical growth from 13 to 19 years. It is this phase when one learns to come across mood swings and start exploring and understanding the creativity within self. Video games now more demanding as digital games are one such area of exploration (Rutter, 2006). Creativity is a key element in developing any virtual world. The passion of artistry, technology, social interaction enhances intra, inter, group and mass communication that generate ideas in improving the virtual world.

Till the early twenty first century this exploration was restricted to the traditional games including outdoor and indoor games wherein no internet was required rather available but it was all about physical and mental effort. For example, cricket, football, kabaddi, kho-kho, hockey, race such games were known among outdoor activities. On the other side, carom, chess, hide-and-seek like games were the restricted ones to entertain the teenagers within the four walls (Hsiao, 2007). The advent of video games which has slowly transformed to digital or online games is changing the mind-set of playing games among the teenagers. They are addicted to various online games depending on category like mission-oriented, violence and so on (Flanagan, 2014).

They tend to adopt the Uses and Gratification Theory (developed by Elihu Katz and Jay Blumler), which focuses on what people do with the media, instead of what media do to the people (as studied by Sarah Turney of the Pennsylvania State University). The used technique believes that audiences are active and willingly expose themselves to media and that the most effective mass media content cannot influence an individual who has 'no use' for it in the environment in which he or she resides. According to a study of Vir Bala Aggarwal and VS Gupta in 2001, the term 'gratification' refers to the rewards and satisfaction experienced by the audiences after the use of media, it helps to explain motivations behind media use and habits of media use or the actual needs satisfaction by the media are called media gratifications. This gratification has several uses namely cognition (the act of coming to know something), diversion (includes stimulation, relaxation, emotional release, reality exploration), social utility (individual's need to affiliate with others) and withdrawal (using the mass media to create a barrier between themselves and other people or other activities).

As this approach relies heavily on surveys based on the actual responses of audience members, the research on above mentioned topic was carried out to prove that people's responses are valid indicators of their motives. At some point the teenagers adopt negative aspects as well which is affecting their mental and physical stamina in the current scenario. Taking a statement from Indian Express, the Blue Whale Challenge believed to be a suicide game wherein a group of administrators or a certain curator gives a participant a task to complete daily for a period of 50 days the final of which is the participant committing suicide across the world proves this point.

Objectives:

- To find which of the two types of games is preferred more by adolescents.
- To see if any of these influences their behavioural communication.
- To find out which medium is used more for playing digital games.

Literature review:

As per research paper 'Teenagers' Usage of Social Networking Media in a South Indian State' (Titto, Nivedhitha, & Pradeep, 2013) more time on internet is spent on social networking sites compared to the time they spend for educational needs. The gratifications obtained from the usage of social networking sites are factor analysed to a four factor structure, namely Communication, Connectivity, Relaxation and User friendliness. The study was conducted in among 556 school students from standard eight to twelve including government and private schools.

According to report 'Teen addicted to Internet games is 'rare' patient in a Delhi hospital' (Kaunain, 2017) a 16-year student glued to the internet game for eight hours a day became distracted when he was away from it for which he had to undergo medication and psychotherapy at a hospital in the national capital. It was an unusual case handled by the doctors.

There are three distinct categories of online games mentioned in 'Control over Virtual Worlds by Game Companies: Issues and Recommendations' research paper (Christophe, 2011). The first is simple online games, a highly disparate category despite its label. The MMOGs (massively multiplayer online games) form the second category which is marked by absence of a pre-scripted story line and the fact that avatars controlled by the users are not pre-determined by the game's developers. The third category MMORPGs (massively multiplayer online role-playing games) which submerge users in a pre-scripted environment of variable complexity usually involve heroic fantasy or science fiction.

Blue Whale Game: What is it in 6 points' news report (Gadgets360staff, 2017) mentions about online game Blue Whale challenge: this 50-day challenge requires participants to receive instructions from an anonymous administrator, and their final task is to commit suicide. This game had resulted to deaths in China, United States and India. The challenge was created by Philipp Budeikin, a 22-year-old Russian, who directly handed out instructions to some children. In an interview this year, he said he made the game to "clean society," as people who participated in it were "biological waste." He has been jailed for three years.

As per timesofindia.com news report 'Blue Whale challenge a 'national problem,' says Supreme Court', Blue Whale challenge was called a national problem by Supreme Court. The apex court also

directed state-run Doordarshan and private television channels to help create awareness about the deadly game, by telecasting the dangers of the game in their prime time programmes. The challenge was termed a 'suicide game,' which manipulated impressionable teenagers to complete a series of dark challenges, like listening to 'dark songs' and self-harming, and ultimately goading the youngster to commit suicide (ANI, 2017)

'Side effects: Deaths caused by video game addiction' news report (Deccan Chronicle, 2016) mentions video games have been here since a few decades. Though it started as a main reason for relaxing or pastime, it has now turned into serious a money-making business and a career for many. However, it is also sad to know that the addiction has many of the younger generations hooked to the gaming console. Be it on your smartphone, gaming console or television set, moderate gaming is considered good for your health. Scientists predict that the brain becomes active and there are signs of better development with certain games.

'The Impact of Technology on the Developing Child' news report (Cris, 2013) states Technology's impact on the 21st century family is fracturing its very foundation, and causing a disintegration of core values that long ago were the fabric that held families together. Juggling school, work, home, and community lives, parents now rely heavily on communication, information, and transportation technology to make their lives faster and more efficient. Children now rely on technology for the majority of their play, grossly limiting challenges to their creativity and imaginations, as well as limiting necessary challenges to their bodies to achieve optimal sensory and motor development.

Methods & Materials:

Primary Data: Initially a pilot study was conducted among respondents aged between 13 to 19 years from class sixth to twelfth, counted as Teenagers in Ranchi and Raipur (state capitals of Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh) through online platform to understand the role of digital games in their lives. Accordingly, the topic of research paper was decided followed by three objectives and three hypotheses. It was applied research. The stratified sampling method was adopted. Survey was the research method focusing specifically on longitudinal survey. 30 teenagers from Raipur and 30 teenagers from Ranchi were decided as target audience.

The data collection of the survey was through questionnaire including 10 objective questions with sub-questions under them. The preliminary work commenced in September 2022 but the survey was conducted in October 2022. As back-to-back festivals were scheduled in the specified month with frequent holidays, the respondents were contacted for filling the questionnaire through Facebook messenger, mails and Whatsapp. Accordingly, the conclusion was drawn.

Secondary Data: This is the review of literature part which had been discussed above.

Results:

Data Collection and Analysis:

Q1.1 Do you play games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	27	90%
NO	3	10%
TOTAL	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	27	90%
NO	3	10%
TOTAL	30	100%

Out of the total 30 respondents in Ranchi, 27 out of total 30 said they play games while 27 respondents of Raipur agreed to the same option.

Q1.2 If yes, which medium is preferred?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
OUTDOOR	13	48%
INDOOR	1	4%
DIGITAL	12	44%
OTHER		
TOTAL	27	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
OUTDOOR	9	33%
INDOOR	4	15%
DIGITAL	14	52%
OTHER		
TOTAL	27	100%

When asked which among the two is preferred, 13 out of 27 respondents of Ranchi said they prefer outdoor games while 14 out of 27 respondents of Raipur said they prefer digital games.

Q2.1 According to you, which games are better?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
TRADITIONAL	21	70%
DIGITAL	9	30%
TOTAL	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
TRADITIONAL	14	47%
DIGITAL	16	53%
TOTAL	30	100%

In the first part of second question, the answers of respondents varied in Ranchi and Raipur with 70% adolescents marking traditional games to be better than digital while 53% adolescents of Raipur marked digital games better than traditional.

Q 2.2 What are the reasons of playing traditional games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Improves physical and mental health	18	60%
Social Communication	8	27%
Other	4	13%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Improves physical and mental health	14	60%
Social Communication	16	53%%
Other	0	0

Total	30	100%
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The second part of question number two asked what the reasons of playing traditional games to which 60% respondents, the majority in Ranchi replied it improving physical and mental health while it was 60% respondents of Raipur felt the same.

Q3. What are the reasons of playing digital games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Easy accessibility	18	60%
Time saving	5	17%
Other	3	10%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Easy accessibility	22	73%
Time saving	5	17%
Other	3	10%
Total	30	100%

Majority of the respondents in both the state capitals play digital games for its easy accessibility. It was clear with 60% teenagers of Ranchi marking this option while 73% Raipur teenagers following the same.

Q4. Which medium is convenient for playing digital games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Desktop	3	10%
Laptop	1	3%
Cell phone	12	40%
Tablet	2	7%
All	11	37%
Other	1	3%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
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Desktop	3	10%
Laptop	1	3%
Cell phone	12	40%
Tablet	2	7%
All	11	37%
Other	1	3%
Total	30	100%

In terms of convenience, majority in Ranchi including 40% respondents play digital games in the cell phone. Similar option is more preferred by Raipur ones with 40% marking this answer.

Q5. Which category of digital games is preferred?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Violence	2	7%
Education	7	23%
Mission Oriented	12	40%
Non-Violence	3	10%
Other	6	20%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Violence	2	7%
Education	16	53%
Mission Oriented	9	30%
Non-Violence	1	3%
Other	6	20%
Total	30	100%

In case of digital games category preference, the choice of both the cities differed with 40% out of 30 respondents in Ranchi choosing mission-oriented category while 53% out of 30 respondents of Raipur selecting education category.

Q 6.1 Do you find any behaviour transformation by playing digital games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	18	60%
NO	12	40%
OTHER	0	0
TOTAL	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	22	73%
NO	7	23%
OTHER	0	0
TOTAL	30	100%

In the first part of sixth question when respondents were asked about behaviour transformation by playing digital games, majority in both cities felt they do feel the change. 60% teenagers in Ranchi selected this option with 73% choosing the same in Raipur.

Q 6.2 If yes, what kind of change is it?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Calm and Composed	8	44%
Aggressive	8	44%
Other	2	12%
Total	18	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Calm and Composed	8	36%
Aggressive	6	28%
Other	8	36%
Total	22	100%

In the second part of the sixth question, when asked what kind of change is it, most in targeted areas could not choose an exact answer by marking other option. There were 44% teenagers of Ranchi choosing this calm and composed option followed by the same number for aggressive option. Meanwhile, in Raipur 36% respondents chose calm and composed while same number chose other option.

Q 7.1 Does digital games affect your communication?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	20	67%
NO	10	33%
TOTAL	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	23	77%
NO	9	23%
TOTAL	30	100%

When it comes to affecting communication, it does as 67% respondents of Ranchi said yes while 77% respondents of Raipur said yes.

Q 7.2 If yes, how?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Introvert	2	10%
In-Depth thinking	4	20%
Talkative	4	20%
Imaginary	9	45%
Other	1	5%
Total	20	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Introvert	2	9%
In-Depth thinking	5	21%
Talkative	8	35%

Imaginary	6	26%
Other	2	9%
Total	23	100%

If they feel the change what kind of change it is, to this 45% respondents of Ranchi chose the imaginary option and 35% respondents chose talkative. This indicated that Ranchi adolescents find change in imaginations and Raipur adolescents find the change with their talkative habit.

Q 8. 1 Do you recommend such games to others?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	17	57%
NO	13	43%
TOTAL	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	20	67%
NO	10	33%
TOTAL	30	100%

Adolescents are recommending such games to others since 57% respondents of Ranchi said they do it and 67% respondents of Raipur said they do it.

Q 8.2 If yes, how?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
By showing demonstration	10	59%
Verbally	7	41%
Other	0	0
Total	20	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
By showing demonstration	7	35%
Verbally	10	50%

Other	3	15%
TOTAL	17	100%

The recommendation mode differs in both cities as 59% respondents show the demonstration of the game in Ranchi while 50% respondents do it through merely through word of mouth.

Q 9. Would you take interest in preparing any of these games?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Certainly	8	27%
Unsure	3	10%
Depends on category	15	50%
Other	4	13%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Certainly	10	33%
Unsure	4	13%
Depends on category	13	44%
Other	3	10%
Total	30	100%

In the ninth question wherein respondents were asked about whether they will take interest in preparing any such games, the adolescents are specific to their choice with depending on category.

Q 10. Do such games divert you from maintaining face to face interaction?

RANCHI	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Completely	9	30%
Never	8	27%
Unsure	10	33%
Other	3	10%
Total	30	100%

RAIPUR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Completely	10	33%
Never	10	33%
Unsure	6	20%
Other	4	14%
Total	30	100%

33% respondents of Ranchi were unsure when it comes to diversion of face-to-face interaction due to digital games while 33% respondents of Raipur never find such a diversion or completely find the distraction.

Conclusion:

Considering the first objective which mentioned which among the two is preferred answers of question number one were analysed wherein out of the total 30 respondents in Ranchi, 27 out of total 30 said they play games while 27 respondents of Raipur agreed to the same option in the first part. In the second part when asked which among the two is preferred, 13 out of 27 respondents of Ranchi said they prefer outdoor games while 14 out of 27 respondents of Raipur said they prefer digital games.

The second objective was does it influence their behaviour. For this question number six was analysed. In the first part of sixth question when respondents were asked about behaviour transformation by playing digital games, majority in both cities felt they do feel the change. 60% teenagers in Ranchi selected this option with 73% choosing the same in Raipur. In the second part of the sixth question, when asked what kind of change it is, most in targeted areas could not choose an exact answer by marking other option. There were 44% teenagers of Ranchi choosing this calm and composed option followed by the same number for aggressive option. Meanwhile, in Raipur 36% respondents chose calm and composed while same number chose other option. The result of sixth question was supported by seventh question which in the first part mentioned that when it comes to affecting communication, it does as 67% respondents of Ranchi said yes while 77% respondents of Raipur said yes. The second part of this question proved that 45% respondents of Ranchi feel imaginary, and 35% respondents of Raipur feel talkative.

The third cum last objective was which medium is preferred. Question number four was taken for this which asked about the medium preference including cell phone, desktop, laptop, tablet, all, and others. Here, majority of teenagers in Ranchi including 40% respondents play digital games in the

cell phone. Similar option was more preferred by Raipur ones with 40% respondents marking this answer.

The way technology is developing, on the other hand it is reflecting the life of literate adolescents who are dependent on digital games, but the popularity of traditional games is vanishing. The entire research proved this scenario. The dependency on cell phones has increased compared to other mediums due to the free or cheap availability of internet or Wi-Fi. The communication of respondents is further affected, shows the surveys.

Discussion:

- 1) The research was limited to two state capitals with 30 respondents each in respective areas. It could have been expanded for better result.
- 2) Out of 30 respondents in each city, 27 agreed that they play digital games but in the remaining nine questions of the survey all the respondents answered to the questions to express their words. This was also counted for analysis as public opinions forms voices of every segment of the society.
- 3) Due to time-crunch, a small number of respondents were taken as sample approached through online platform covering mails and social media and mobile applications. It could have been done face-to-face and expanded to other age genres as well for understanding the significance of the study at large.
- 4) One or two subjective questions could have been added at the end of the questionnaire for better comparison in the survey and bringing out more results for further study as well as understanding.

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